

STATISTICAL RESULTS

Table 1

Variable: Entrepreneurship

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage
Poor	17	8,5	8,5
Fair	50	25,0	25,0
Good	133	66,5	66,5
Total	200	100,0	100,0

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The results indicate that among women artisans, 66.5% exhibit a high level of entrepreneurship, 25.0% show a medium level, and 8.5% have a low level. Overall, these findings demonstrate a predominantly favorable entrepreneurial capacity, although there is still a need for strengthening within a small sector.

Table 2

Dimension: Entrepreneurial Commitment

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage
Poor	3	1,5	1,5
Fair	89	44,5	44,5
Good	108	54,0	54,0
Total	200	100,0	100,0

Data Analysis and Interpretation

54.0% of women artisans exhibit a high level of entrepreneurship, 44.5% show a medium level, and 1.5% have a low level, highlighting a predominance of positive commitment with opportunities for improvement.

Table 3***Dimension: Business Management***

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage
Poor	18	9,0	9,0
Fair	59	29,5	29,5
Good	123	61,5	61,5
Total	200	100,0	100,0

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

61.5% of artisan women present a high level of business management, 29.5% a medium level, and 9.0% a low level. This indicates a predominantly favorable management situation, with identified needs for strengthening.

Table 4***Dimension, Leadership, and Collaboration***

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage
Poor	11	5,5	5,5
Fair	74	37,0	37,0
Good	115	57,5	57,5
Total	200	100,0	100,0

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Female entrepreneurship demonstrates competencies in leadership and collaboration, as 57.5% of artisan women possess a high level, 37.0% a medium level, and 5.5% a low level.

Table 5***Dimension, Customer Relationship***

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage
Poor	34	17,0	17,0
Fair	86	43,0	43,0
Good	80	40,0	40,0
Total	200	100,0	100,0

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

43.0% of artisan women present a medium level in customer relationship, 40.0% a high level, and 17.0% a low level. This indicates acceptable practices with identified needs for strengthening in commercial engagement.

Table 6

Variable, Innovation

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage
Poor	100	50,0	50,0
Fair	57	28,5	28,5
Good	43	21,5	21,5
Total	200	100,0	100,0

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

The fact that 50.0% of artisan women exhibit low levels of innovation, while 21.5% demonstrate high levels of innovation, reveals limitations in their innovative capacity that affect their competitiveness in the tourism sector.

Table 7

Dimension, Entrepreneurship and Innovation

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage
Poor	107	53,5	53,5
Fair	37	18,5	18,5
Good	56	28,0	28,0
Total	200	100,0	100,0

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

53.5% of artisan women show low levels of entrepreneurship and innovation, indicating limitations that affect their competitiveness and the need for strengthening strategies for their integration into the regional tourism sector.

Table 8

Dimensión, Transformación digital

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage
Poor	109	54,5	54,5
Fair	50	25,0	25,0
Good	41	20,5	20,5
Total	200	100,0	100,0

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

54.5% of artisan women exhibit a low level of technological adoption, indicating digital limitations that affect their competitiveness and require strengthening of digital transformation.

Table 9

Dimension, Adaptation and Innovation Capacity

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage
Poor	111	55,5	55,5
Fair	55	27,5	27,5
Good	34	17,0	17,0
Total	200	100,0	100,0

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

55.5% of artisan women exhibit low adaptive and innovative capacity, which limits their response to the tourism environment and requires strengthening strategies to improve their competitiveness.

Table 10

Dimension, Innovative Leadership

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage
Poor	98	49,0	49,0
Fair	56	28,0	28,0
Good	46	23,0	23,0
Total	200	100,0	100,0

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

49% of artisan women demonstrate low innovative leadership, indicating restrictions in their decision-making capacity, change management, and strategic positioning, which negatively impacts the competitiveness and sustainability of their businesses.